

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GLASS SHORT FIBER/WOOD POWDER/POLYPROPYLENE HYBRID COMPOSITES

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1 General Introduction

During the last few years, polypropylene (PP) incorporated with particulate fillers has been gained high interests. Since as well known, PP not only exhibits excellent stiffness property and environment adaptability, but also has a good processability allowing accepting different types of fillers. It is known that the fillers are the most often used materials to reduce the production costs and optimize the production properties such as rigidity, strength, dimensional stability, crystallinity, electrical, thermal conductivity and so on. Although fillers also have a detrimental effect on other properties of filler reinforced thermoplastics such as the impact properties and deformability, incorporating fillers can help to increase the application areas of polypropylene [1-4].

On the other hand, owing to low prices, low density, ecological and economical advantage, less health hazards, and the steadily rising performance of technical and standard plastics, the demand for natural filler incorporate composites has been increased in various application areas such as automotive components, building materials, and electrical engineering. In particularly, more recently, the critical discussion about the preservation of natural resources and recycling has led to a renewed interest concerning natural materials with the focus on renewable raw materials. Particularly, in automotive field, natural fiber composites are promising materials used for interior and exterior parts. Not only because they are helpful to reduce the overall weight of the vehicle which can increase the fuel efficiency, but also they are helpful to keep the sustainability of the manufacturing materials. Especially in Japan, material contains over 50% of biodegradability component is deemed to eco-materials which can be disposed as combustible waste [5-8]. Among all the natural material, wood is

considered as one of the attractive alternatives for reinforcing thermoplastics. The use of wood as reinforcement for the composites has received increasing attentions recent years both by the academic sector and the industry as inexpensive filler to increase the mechanical properties and thermal stabilities of thermoplastic or to reduce raw material costs. Because the wood flour can be derived from sawdust, pulp mill wood residue, bark, nutshell, and straw. Therefore, as potential application, which are furniture components, door moldings, floor systems for light frame construction, and packaging pallets, wood reinforced thermoplastic composites are commercially attractive for high volume applications [9-13].

As a kind of natural fiber, wood primarily consist of: cellulose, hemicelluloses, pectin and lignin. Therefore, unlike synthetic fibers, although wood composites combine good mechanical properties with a low specific mass, the high level of moisture absorption by natural fibers, and the poor bonding properties between natural fiber and matrix would potentially have detrimental effects on the natural fiber reinforced composites. In addition, as filler form, the poor compatibility between reinforcement and polymer matrix would also lead to a poor distribution and local area concentration. That will result in the whole green composite is not satisfied the needs of the society at present [14-16]. To improve the properties of the composites, natural fibers can be modified by physical and chemical methods to improve the interfacial and distribution properties. Since most natural fiber is heterogeneous complex polymer, it provide a high possibility to allow that different chemical groups reacting with the natural fiber. Moreover, adding some processing aids and compatibilizers is also considered as a suitable way especially to facilitate the natural filler dispersion and induce bond formation between filler

and polymer matrix. Another possible way appears to be very important is the fiber hybridization by combining two or more different types of fibers in a common matrix to get a range of properties that can not be obtained with a single kind of reinforcement. Combining natural fibers with stronger synthetic fibers like glass, carbon, which could offer a better optimum balance between performance and cost. These composites, which utilize two different types of fibers, are termed to hybrid composites. The most widely synthetic reinforcement used in hybridization is glass fiber because of its high strength, stiffness, and corrosion resistance. By incorporation the glass fiber into natural fiber composites, the penetration resistance and damage tolerance of natural fiber reinforced composites could be improved greatly [18-20]. In Carlo Santulli's [21] paper, the impact properties of glass/plant fiber hybrid laminates have been reviewed, trying to obtain materials with sufficient impact properties, whilst retaining a reduced cost and a substantial environmental gain. It is found that the successful development of glass/plant fiber hybrid laminates would benefit from fulfilling the following objectives: Introduction of a larger (global) volume of fibers in the composite; Improved effectiveness of interfaces in dissipating impact damage or improved intermingling of fibers; Modification of the geometry or study of the configurations in order to maximize impact properties. S.S. Morye, R.P. Wool [18] has reported the mechanical properties of glass/flax hybrid composites based on a novel modified soybean oil matrix material. The mechanical properties of the composites were found to depend upon the glass/flax ratio and the arrangement of fibers in the composite. On proper selection of the arrangement of fibers in the composite, the glass fibers and flax fibers were found to act synergistically resulting in an improved flexural and impact performance. Influence of interfacial adhesion on the structural and mechanical behavior of PP-banana/glass hybrid composites has investigated by Sanjay K. Nayak et al [22]. The rate of water absorption for the hybrid composites was decreased due to the presence of glass fiber and coupling agent. Mechanical tests revealed that the mechanical properties of the hybrid composites could be improved at certain banana to glass ratio and with the coupling agent. Thermal analysis also confirmed the enhancement in melting point, crystallization temperature, and onset thermal degradation temperature. Therefore, from the foregoing, it is clearly to understand that the

production of glass/plant fiber hybrid laminates has been explored during recent years, trying to obtain materials with sufficient mechanical properties, which also maintains a reduced cost and a substantial environmental gain.

In this study, 3 kinds of Glass/PP and 3 kinds of Wood/PP composites have been fabricated by injection process with reinforcement contents of 15, 30 and 51wt%, respectively. In addition, glass fiber/wood powder/pp hybrid composites were prepared at a fixed reinforcement to matrix ratio of 51:49. 4 kinds of hybrid specimens with glass fiber/wood powder ratios of 41:10, 31:20, 21:30, and 11:40 were fabricated. The wood dispersion condition was evaluated by modulus prediction results and SEM observation results and the glass short fiber orientation was examined by fiber number counting approach. The effect of hybridization content on the mechanical properties of the composites was evaluated based on tensile test and Izod impact test.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials and composite preparation

Polypropylene, as block polymer, with a melt index of 30g/10min (B3050, Idemitsu Kosan Co., Ltd) was used as matrix because it is a widely used plastic in the automotive industry that can be easily injection molded. Glass short fiber (Owens Corning Co., Ltd, Japan) and wood powder which is soft wood type from *Cryptomeria japonica* (from trees in Hiroshima prefecture, Japan) were used as reinforcements to fabricate the glass short fiber/wood particle/pp dumbbell shape specimens by injection molding method. Before injection, wood powder and glass short fiber was compounded with PP through compounding machine to get wood/pp and glass/pp pellets respectively. The compositions of the pellets were as same as their final products, and after compounding, those pellets were feed into the injection machine. 10 kinds of dumbbell shaped specimens were prepared as listed in Table.1. In details, WP15~WP51 composites were Wood/PP contain wood particle contents of 15, 30 and 51wt%, respectively. GF15~GF51 composites were Glass/PP contain glass short fiber contents of 15, 30 and 51wt%, respectively. While the last 4 composites were glass short fiber/wood particle/pp hybrid composites at a fixed reinforcement to matrix ratio of 51:49 with glass fiber/wood powder ratios of

41:10, 31:20, 21:30, and 11:40. In this study, the ‘Green degree’ was introduced which defined as the weight percentage of natural components in composite materials and the equation was shown in the following,

$$\text{Green degree (\%)} = (W_N/W_C) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where, W_N and W_C are total weight of natural component and total weight of composite, respectively.

All of the test pieces were fabricated by using a 30-ton TOYO PSS TT-30F6 injection molding machine at a barrel temperature of between 150-210°C. Here should be mentioned that both before compounding and injection process, wood powder and pellets contain wood were dried in an oven set at 90°C for at least 16 hours to remove the moisture.

Table.1 Material composition

Specimen Code	Glass fiber (wt%)	Wood powder (wt%)	Polypropylene (wt%)	Others (wt%)	Green degree (%)
WP15	0	15	83	2	15
WP30	0	30	68	2	30
WP51	0	51	47	2	51
GF15	15	0	83	2	0
GF30	30	0	68	2	0
GF51	51	0	47	2	0
GF41-WP10	41	10	47	2	10
GF31-WP20	31	20	47	2	20
GF21-WP30	21	30	47	2	30
GF11-WP40	11	40	47	2	40

2.2 Tensile test

For tensile test, the grip length is 115 mm, and strain was measured by using a dynamic extensometer measurement (Instron, catalogue 2620-601), which was fixed onto the central surface of the specimen by a rubber band. Tensile test was conducted on an Instron Universal Testing Machine (Type 4206) under a nominal test speed of 1.0 mm/min in accordance with ISO-527. 3 pieces were repeated.

2.3 Izod impact test

Izod impact test was performed on the Impact tester (Toyoseiki), pendulum 5.5 J in accordance with ADTM D 256-05. The size of the specimen was 10 mm×60 mm, V-notch was used. Five specimens were repeated.

3 Experimental results and discussion

3.1 Mechanical properties of Glass/PP & Wood/PP

Fig.1 shows the tensile stress-strain curves of Glass/PP & Wood/PP composites. It was noted that for both composites, the stress-strain relationship changed from ductile to brittle behavior with the increasing of the reinforcement content. However, for Glass/PP, this change was very obviously. In addition, even incorporating only 15wt% glass short fiber, the elongation at break of the Glass/PP composite decreased significantly. While for Wood/PP, this change happened progressively with the increase of the wood particle content. Fig.2 shows the tensile modulus and strength of Glass/PP & Wood/PP composites. For both composites, the tensile modulus and strength increased with the increasing of the reinforcement content. It can be considered that both glass short fiber and wood particle show the reinforced effect to the PP resin in the composite structure. However, compared to the Glass/PP composite, the increase ratio was much lower for Wood/PP composite. In details, the tensile modulus of Glass/PP increased 96%, and 204% after incorporating 15 and 30wt% glass short fiber, respectively. While for Wood/PP composite, the increasing ratios were 25% and 64% respectively. Particularly, for Wood/PP, the tensile strength increased with the increasing of wood content up to 30wt%. After then, it started to decrease.

(a) Tensile stress-strain curves of Glass/PP composites

(b) Tensile stress-strain curves of Wood/PP composites

Fig.1. Tensile stress-strain curves of Glass/PP & Wood/PP composites

(a) Tensile modulus and strength of Glass/PP composite

(b) Tensile modulus and strength of Wood/PP composite

Fig.2. Tensile properties of Glass/PP & Wood/PP composites

Izod impact properties of Glass/PP & Wood/PP composites were presented in fig.3. The Izod strength for Glass/PP composite increased with the increasing of the glass content, and all Glass/PP composites showed higher Izod strength values than neat PP. It is considered that the impact energy can be transferred from the PP matrix to glass fiber and lead to the increase of the impact resistance of the material. However, for Wood/PP, it decreased with the increasing of the filler content and the Izod strength of all Wood/PP composites showed lower values than neat PP. It is apparent that the toughness of the composite decreased after incorporating the filler. The immobilization of the matrix by the filler so that the latter fails to deform before failure is considered as one of the reasons leading to the decreasing of the Izod strength. Additionally, poor

wetting of the powder by polypropylene, giving rise to poor interfacial adhesion between the filler and the polymer matrix resulting in weak interfacial regions is also considered one of the reasons.

Fig.3. Izod impact properties of Glass/PP & Wood/PP composites

SEM observations were carried out to examine the wood particle distribution state in Wood/PP composite. In this study, in order to give a more distinct detection of the wood powder, etching process was performed before SEM on the polished specimens. CRP-MARS etchant provided from Okuno Chemical Industries Co., Ltd was used as etching solution. The fracture surface observations of wood/PP composite with different wood contents after etching process were shown in fig.4, it was obviously that after etching, the wood powder was etched and left behind lots of voids on the fracture surface. Those voids distribution of the specimen after etching was considered equal to wood distribution. It is obviously that at low wood particle content composites (below 30wt% wood content), wood powder was distributed uniformly and separately in the PP matrix. However, at a high wood powder content composite, i.e., 51wt%, wood powder agglomerated in some regions and the distribution of the powder in PP matrix became worse and worse with increasing of the wood powder content. It is well known that the type of filler, distribution of filler and interaction between matrix and filler are the most important factors which will affect the mechanical properties of filler reinforced composites. In this study, the agglomeration of the wood powder, poor dispersion of the wood powder in the matrix is considered the main reasons which led to the low tensile properties at high wood powder content composite.

Fig.4. Fracture surface observations on the polished Wood/PP surfaces with different wood contents after etching process

3.2 Modulus prediction of filler reinforced composites by using Nielsen equation

The most prominent of physical effects of fillers is the stiffening or modulus increase that they caused in composites. For particulate filled composites, a number of equations for prediction of the modulus have been proposed with different methods. In this study, the elastic modulus of the wood/PP composite was predicted by using Nielsen equation which was shown as follows:

$$M/M_1 = (1 + ABV_f) / (1 - B\psi V_f) \quad (2)$$

$$A = K_E - 1 \quad (3)$$

$$B = (M_2/M_1 - 1) / (M_2/M_1 + A) \quad (4)$$

$$\psi = (1 - P_f) / P_f^2 \times V_f \quad (5)$$

Where, M , M_1 and M_2 are modulus of the composite, matrix, and filler respectively; K_E is the Einstein coefficient; V_f is the fractional filler volume; and P_f is the packing fraction of the filler at maximum filler concentration. The constant K_E accounts for the shape of the filler particles and poisson's ratio of the matrix, respectively.

The predicted results for elastic modulus of wood powder composites by using Nielsen equation were

shown in fig.5. It is found that the predicted elastic modulus were in good agreement with experimental values up to 30wt%. However, after that, as filler content increased, Nielsen equation tends to overestimate the elastic modulus of the composite. That is mainly because that Nielsen equation appears to be more relevant to materials with low concentrations of non-interactive spheres. Therefore, it is considered that the inappropriate predicting modulus at high filler content is due to the aggregation and poor distribution of the wood powder in the PP matrix. This result further explained the importance of the well wood dispersion in high wood content composite.

Fig.5. Correlation between experimental and prediction elastic modulus by using Nielsen equation

3.3 Mechanical properties of hybrid composites

The effect of wood powder content on tensile properties of the hybrid composites are plotted in fig.6. For tensile modulus (fig.6 (a)), it is noted that it was regularly decreased with the increasing of wood powder ratio. That is easily to detect because the glass fiber owns much higher elastic modulus compared to wood powder, at fixed reinforcement content, with increasing of wood powder content, the glass fiber content decreased. However, it was noted that the elastic modulus of the glass short fiber/wood particle/pp hybrid composite with 41wt% glass short fiber and 10wt% wood powder content shows similar value to the Glass/PP composite with 45wt% glass short fiber. On the other hand, the tensile strength which plotted in fig.6 (b) also decreased with the increasing of wood powder ratio. In particularly, the decrease ratio of the tensile strength increased after the wood content attained 30wt%. That is considered due to the wood powder aggregate at high wood content and led to a much severer decrease of the strength.

(a) Tensile modulus of glass short fiber/wood particle/pp hybrid composites

(b) Tensile strength of glass short fiber/wood particle/pp hybrid composites

Fig.6. Tensile properties of glass short fiber/wood particle/pp hybrid composites

The Izod impact properties of the glass short fiber/wood particle/pp hybrid composites were shown in fig.7. It is noted that at fixed reinforcement content, the Izod strength decreased with the decreasing of the glass fiber content. However, even the Izod strength decreased significantly with the decreasing of the glass fiber content, it was considered with appropriate material design, it is still possible to get hybrid material with comparable high mechanical properties with high green degree. That is because the Izod strength of hybrid composite with 30wt% wood powder and 21wt% glass short fiber still shows similar value to the neat PP. This value of the hybrid composite is even higher than that of Wood/PP composite contains 51wt% wood content.

Fig.7. Izod impact properties of glass short fiber/wood particle/pp hybrid composites

It is well known that the mechanical properties of short fiber reinforced plastics depend on a lot of factors including fiber orientation, fiber length distribution and so on. In this study, the glass short fiber orientation of the hybrid composites was measured, and only two main fiber orientation directions are considered as 0° and 90° to the flow direction, respectively. The wood particle filled polymer was regarded as a new effective matrix to be reinforced by glass short fiber. Wood and glass were uniformly and stochastically distributed in the pure polymer matrix [23].

The glass fiber orientation in this study is measured by using SEM observation on a polished section of the hybrid composite. An example of the marking method was shown in fig.8. The circle shape of the glass fiber was defined as 0 degree to the flow direction, while the ellipse shape of the glass fiber was defined as 90 degree to the flow direction.

Fig.8. Marking of glass fibers to define the orientation direction of each fiber. The circle marks represent glass fibers oriented in 0 degree to the flow direction while those oriented in 90 degree are marked with ellipse shape: (a) before marking; and (b) after marking

The SEM micrograph in fig.9 (a) & fig.10 (a) showed the polished fracture surfaces of GF41WP10 and GF11WP40 hybrid composites. The glass fibers were marked as shown in fig.9 (b & c) & fig.10 (b &

c) and measured fiber numbers by image J analysis software. Results showed that the ratio of glass short fiber orientated in 0 degree and 90 degree directions were 94% and 6% respectively for GF41WP10 hybrid composite; 93% and 7% respectively for GF31WP20 hybrid composite; 92% and 8% respectively for GF21WP30 hybrid composite; and 88% and 12% respectively for GF11WP40 hybrid composite. Compared with the results in the previous study, the glass short fiber orientation of the Glass/PP composite with 10wt% glass fiber, the ratios of glass fiber orientated in 0 degree and 90 degree directions were 90% and 10%, respectively. This result indicted that incorporating glass fiber into Wood/PP system didn't affect the glass short fiber orientation significantly.

Fig.9. SEM micrograph of fracture surface of GF41WP10 hybrid composite: (a) polished fracture surface of GF41WP10; (b) circle shape marks represent glass fibers oriented in 0 degree to the flow direction; (c) ellipse shape marks represent glass fibers oriented in 90 degree

Fig.10. SEM micrograph of fracture surface of GF11WP40 hybrid composite: (a) polished fracture surface of GF11WP40; (b) circle shape marks represent glass fibers oriented in 0 degree to the flow direction; (c) ellipse shape marks represent glass fibers oriented in 90 degree

4 Conclusion

In this study, 3 kinds of Glass/PP, 3 kinds of Wood/PP composites and 4 kinds of glass short fiber/wood particle/pp hybrid composites were fabricated by injection molding process. The wood dispersion condition was evaluated by modulus prediction results and SEM observation results and the glass short fiber orientation was examined by fiber number counting approach. The effect of hybridization content on the mechanical properties of the composites was evaluated based on tensile test and Izod impact test.

Results showed that for Wood/PP composite, the tensile properties increased much more slowly with the increasing of the wood content after the wood content over 30wt%, especially for the tensile strength, which even decreased. The agglomeration of the wood powder, poor dispersion of the wood powder in the matrix is considered the main reasons. In addition, at fixed glass short fiber/wood particle content, the mechanical property of the hybrid composite was regularly decreased with the decrease of glass fiber ratio. The decrease ratio of the tensile strength increased after the wood content attained

30wt%. That is considered due to the wood aggregate at high wood content and led to a much severer decrease of the strength. In particular, it is noted that incorporating glass fiber into Wood/PP system didn't affect the glass short fiber orientation significantly.

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